

MODELLING AND SIMULATION OF CROWD EVACUATION WITH COGNITIVE BEHAVIOUR USING FUZZY LOGIC

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Abstract

Emotions are the common properties involved during emergencies. Various emotions are observed during emergency such as panic, fear, sad and anxiety which will lead to behaviour and trajectories during the evacuation. Even there are many studies of computational simulation model with crowd behavioural studies, yet there are still gaps of real evacuation due to scarcity of real data and mostly assumption is made on simulated model. In this paper, investigation on how the key emotions turn into behavior are studied from the real emergency video. The key emotions extracted are panic and confuse which is observed from the real emergency video. These emotions are then map to psychological theories adopt from Lazarus Theory of emotions and stress. Due to the uncertainties in human behaviour, fuzzy approach is chosen to map linguistic value to speed (numerical) which will then lead to behavioural results. The simulation results show that the inclusion of emotions via fuzzy rules has resulted 59.2% accuracy compare to non-fuzzy 46.6% to real emergency trajectories data.

1 INTRODUCTION

Gathering trend in current society in celebrating event has become a universal phenomenon.

Crowd gathering consists of peoples from small to large scales. In a big event, a tiny misconception can easily get many people to be out of control [1]. Emergency often creates emotions (psychological) such as panic and stress in the crowd. The human emotional transition between normal to panic state is due to extreme event which is beyond control. Crowds easily losses irrational behaviours in emergency evacuation when emotions such as anger, anxiety spirals and develop to high level [2]. Due to this reason, understanding the key emotions involved and behavioural action during evacuation is critical to minimize loss in tragedies that have grown rapidly.

In recent years, there have been many studies attempt to investigate and improve crowd emergency evacuations [3]. According to Xiaoshan and [4] in order to improve crowd safety in public assembly places, one have to understand human and social behaviours during emergencies. Past studies of emergency evacuation have revealed that there are three crowd behavioural factors that can influence evacuation results namely psychological, environment and perception factors [5].

Current models have generally ignored insights of human behaviors from the perspective of psychology [6]. According to [7], human intelligence and psychology play a major role in evacuation process but it is not sufficient considering only traditional methods with weak detailed features and efficiency. Existing models have been

trying to incorporate realistic pedestrian behavior into the model by learning mechanism such as from the researcher observation [8] or virtual reality. However, due to scarcity of real behavioural data, many computational tools for the emergency simulation rely on assumptions that is inconsistent and unrealistic.

Therefore, this has explain the need of incorporating more realistic human behaviour involving psychological and perceptions of human into the evacuation models in imitating the real behavior of human as it is crucial.

2 Integration of Fuzzy rules in Proposed Evacuation Model with Key Emotions Learn from Real Emergency

The proposed model was aim to obtain a human-like evacuation model which adopt key emotions as observed from real video into our approach. Without neglecting the most important attribute during emergency which is stress, Lazarus theory [9] of cognitive and appraisal in stressful situation are chosen to be included in the proposed model. The stage that being focus in this model is emotion-focused coping. Figure 1 show Transactional Model of Emotions, Stress and Coping by Lazarus map to the proposed model.

Figure 1: Transactional Model of Emotions, Stress and Coping by Lazarus map to our work

Comparing Our model to Lazarus as in 1, our model is in agreement with Lazarus’ theory of

stress [9], where primary and secondary appraisal stage is being consider not only at the initial point but throughout the simulation process.

2.1 Modelling Crowd from Real Emergency Data

Within this paper, the real video evacuation case in Dam Square, Amsterdam on 4th of May 2010 is analysed and compared to previous work by [1]. Observing the above panic video, information on emotions is extracted. We can see there are 2 types of behavior in the emergency evacuation which is wait or minor action. This emotion is assume as confuse. Another types of behavior is run very fast due to panic. The emotion panic is define as P while Confuse as C.

Based on these observation, the 2 key emotions is consider to be part of reaction when stressor is imposed. The key emotions is control by the distance of the person to the affected point which we define the stressor as S.

3 PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Validation of the model is done by comparing the trajectories accuracy during the evacuation in the simulation and in the emergency video data. The simulation position results of each agent at each time step are compared using Euclidean Distance formula and the difference of the value are compared to the original evacuation data. The average error per time step for all agent is calculated and resulting for the accuracy percentage of 35 agents which will be shown in further discussion.

The comparison is made on Non-Fuzzy model without emotion and Non-Fuzzy Model with different combination of emotions at the initial point to get the best trajectories accuracy. Then we compare the best Non-Fuzzy Model with our proposed Fuzzy Model and previous models as in Table. 1.

3.1 Simulation Results Comparison on the best Non-Fuzzy Model with Fuzzy Model

The Non-Fuzzy model in this simulation has the same flow of Fuzzy Model except for emotions influenced. The agents position in proposed Fuzzy Model have the same starting point but the behaviour may differ to the last time steps as in below screenshot:

The red circle is the stressor where the crowd fleeing from and the two big dot in dark green is the exit doors. There are three exit in these simulations.

(a) A Non-Fuzzy Model

(b) A Fuzzy Model

Figure 2: Timestep = 49 Comparison for Non-Fuzzy and Fuzzy Model

In the last time step of simulation as in Figure. 2, different pattern of crowd behaviour are circles and can be seen on fuzzy and non-fuzzy model. Fuzzy model has shown some influence of emotions in the neighbouring agent and the exit visibility of each agent thus changing the direction of the original 3 agents to the opposite direction.

From the result we can conclude that:

1. Fuzzy model have the most lesser error compared to other models from literature.
2. Fuzzy model perform better than Non-Fuzzy model with and without emotions.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, the proposed model have shown the need of human-like integration into the crowd evacuation simulation to mimic real evacuation scenario.

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Table 1: Comparison of Model Average Error

Model	Average Error (meter)
Fuzzy	0.408
ASCRIBE [1]	0.541
Helbing [10]	0.585
The Best Non-Fuzzy with emotion	0.561
Non-Fuzzy	0.534

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